

Statistical Ensemble of Canonical Modes

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Abstract

By extending metric space to expression in hash of directed graph, spatiotemporal observation could be described in matrix quantized state. And three modes of canonical approach in statistical ensemble would be discussed in axiomatic simulation universe.

1 Introduction

In a perspective of matrix-graph relation, scalar could be represented as two row vector v_1, v_2 production as $v_1 \cdot v_2^T$. In sense of keeping ordinal of each particle being countable, this graph-matrix relation could be interpreted in an interaction of particle as a form of energy.

2 Analytical Extension of Graph-Metric Space

While the idea of contraction in metric space gives a chance of graph being non-loss hashable format of scalar[1], matrix gives a relation in graph, conserving its ordinal attribute. By following corollary from understanding Fermat's Last Theorem [7]:

$$\text{Let } a^n + b^n = c^n,$$

$$a = a_1 \cdot i_1 + a_2 \cdot i_2 + \cdots + a_p \cdot i_p,$$

$$b = b_1 \cdot j_1 + b_2 \cdot j_2 + \cdots + b_q \cdot j_q,$$

$$c = c_1 \cdot k_1 + c_2 \cdot k_2 + \cdots + c_r \cdot k_r \quad (a_{\forall x}, b_{\forall x}, c_{\forall x}, p, q, r \in \mathbf{N}^+), \quad (i_{\forall x}, j_{\forall x}, k_{\forall x} \in \mathbf{C})$$

$$\text{Let } \vec{v}_a = (a_1, a_2, \cdots, a_p), \vec{v}_i = (i_1, i_2, \cdots, i_p),$$

$$\vec{v}_b = (b_1, b_2, \cdots, b_q), \vec{v}_j = (j_1, j_2, \cdots, j_q),$$

$$\vec{v}_c = (c_1, c_2, \cdots, c_r), \vec{c}_k = (k_1, k_2, \cdots, k_r) \Rightarrow (\vec{v}_a \cdot \vec{v}_i)^n + (\vec{v}_b \cdot \vec{v}_j)^n = (\vec{v}_c \cdot \vec{v}_k)^n$$

$$\Rightarrow [\text{In size of matrix}] ((1 \times p) \cdot (p \times 1))^n + ((1 \times q) \cdot (q \times 1))^n = ((1 \times r) \cdot (r \times 1))^n$$

$$\Rightarrow n^{(\max p)+(\max q)} = r^n \quad (n \in \mathbf{N}^+) \Rightarrow n = 1 \text{ or } 2 \Rightarrow 2^2 \leq a^2 + b^2 \leq 2^{a^2+b^2}$$

This implies a number in any complex field could be rearranged by graph conserving ordinal attribute. As atomic energy consists itself by a countable form with keeping their topological boundary, we could apply this implication to the atom which is (would be) a form of quantized energy.

3 Larger to Deep Field Observation

If every state of observation could be quantized in ordinal, relation between observation of larger to deep field could be related within. Continuing from what has been discussed in understanding of observing reality [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Assuming Field } \exists F \text{ at given period } t, LFO_t(\exists F) &= \frac{SR_t - CR_t}{SR_t} \\ \implies (\text{Mostly}) 0 \leq LFO_t(\exists F, R) &\leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

Note that, by preceding definition, field at period t is related mainly to convergence or divergence of spatiotemporal when observation distance is far enough. What has been said to be ‘mostly’ is that there is a possibility of distraction or extension when considering additional complex plain. Again, like what said before, LFO could be also expressed into quantized graph by their each observation.

$$\begin{aligned} n_o &= n(\text{Partial Observation } \forall O \text{ at time } t) \\ LFO &= \left\{ \begin{array}{c} \vec{v}_1 \\ \vec{v}_2 \\ \vec{v}_3 \\ \dots \\ \vec{v}_{n_o} \end{array} \right\} \implies \text{Partial Observation } PO \cdot LFO = \text{Total Energy Observed } TEO \end{aligned}$$

4 Extended usage of matrix

If scalar could be extended in an expression of vector and matrix as a expression of basis of span, matrix that represents energy itself gains duality in set of construction. In ordinal perspective by given contraction as span \vec{v} , interaction itself could be contained in an regularity in given quantized energy amount as E . In cardinal perspective by quantized energy amount as E , next interaction decided by given contraction amount could be spread out.

Consequently, by given equation to calculate Total Energy Observed TEO [4]:

$$\begin{aligned} TEO_{AO,E} &= \sum_n^{N(AO)} LFO(AO, OG_n, F) \cdot TEO_{AO,E} \cdot POD_{AO,OG_n} \\ &\quad \cdot (1 - OE(E))(1 - ME(E))(1 - PE(E)) \\ \text{Optimal } t_{\text{wanted}}^* &= \arg \max_t TEO_{AO,E} \\ \text{Optimal } t_{\text{actual}}^* &= \arg \max_t (TEO_{AO,E} - CR_t + SR_t) \\ &\quad (CR_t > 0, SR_t > 0) \\ \exists E &\Leftrightarrow \text{Optimal } t_{\text{actual}}^* = \arg \max_t (TEO_{AO,E} - CR_t + SR_t) \approx 0 \\ \implies TEO &= \sum_t^{\forall t} (\vec{v}_t \cdot TEO_{AO,E} \cdot POD_{AO,OG_n} \\ &\quad \cdot (1 - OE(E))(1 - ME(E))(1 - PE(E)) + SR_t - CR_t) \\ &\Rightarrow \sum_t^{\forall t} \left(\frac{SR_t - CR_t}{SR_t} \cdot PO_t \cdot (1 - OE(E))(1 - ME(E))(1 - PE(E)) + SR_t - CR_t \right) \end{aligned}$$

If limiting \vec{v}_t three-dimension:

Figure 1: Effect of Einstein field equation in energy perspective

$$\left(\text{Decomposing at period } t \right) \frac{SR - CR}{SR} = \left\| \int \left(\nabla \cdot \frac{\Delta SR - \Delta CR}{SR} \right) dt \right\|$$

While calculating each axis of ∇ in assumed three vector:

$$\text{In } \mathbb{R}^3, \left\| \int \left(\nabla \cdot \frac{\Delta SR - \Delta CR}{SR} \right) dt \right\| = \left\| \vec{SR} - \vec{1} \right\| = \left\| \vec{1} - \vec{SR} \right\| = \frac{1}{2}(\cos 2\theta + 1)$$

Note that, this could be interpreted as a curvature in a space which could be another form in Einstein Field Equation. And this implies correlation in gravity also by:

$$|E_{Gravity} \cdot E_{Electromagnetic}| \leq \cos \theta$$

5 Phase Transition of Energy-Matter

The result from Einstein field equation affecting energy expression implies amount of energy that added as electromagnetic gravitational energy causes not only spin of particle to be in specific boundary, but also boundary phase of energy that interacts with.

As ordered in fermion spin, matter has distribution of Fermi-Dirac statistics.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Assuming that, } \sum_i \bar{n}_i &= N \\ \Rightarrow \bar{n}(\epsilon_i) &= g_i \bar{n}_i = \frac{g_i}{e^{(\epsilon_i - \mu)/k_B T} + 1} \\ \sum_i \bar{n}(\epsilon_i) &= E \end{aligned}$$

where κ_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, ϵ_i is the energy of the single-particle state i , and μ is the total chemical potential [2]. And sum by all states of single-particle, the distribution normalizes.

There are three known ways to explain ensembles resulting in phase state. Grand-canonical, canonical, micro-canonical each has their own relation with describing ensemble.

Grand-canonical ensemble describes itself by the equation of its own by expectation in given energy within law of conservation.

Canonical ensemble describes itself by chaining free energy given by the sum of other ensembles of energy states, which resembles with preceding discussion of Einstein field equation.

$$\begin{aligned}
Z_i(N - n_i) &\equiv \sum_{n_1, n_2, \dots}^{(i)} e^{-\beta(n_1 \epsilon_1 + n_2 \epsilon_2 + \dots)} \\
\Rightarrow \bar{n}_i &= \frac{\sum_{n_1, n_2, \dots} n_i e^{-\beta(n_1 \epsilon_1 + n_2 \epsilon_2 + \dots + n_i \epsilon_i + \dots)}}{\sum_{n_1, n_2, \dots} e^{-\beta(n_1 \epsilon_1 + n_2 \epsilon_2 + \dots + n_i \epsilon_i + \dots)}} = \frac{1}{[Z_i(N)/Z_i(N-1)] e^{\beta \epsilon_i} + 1} \\
&= \frac{1}{e^{(\epsilon_i - \mu)/k_B T} + 1} \left(\Rightarrow e^{\epsilon_i - \mu} = \left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right)^{\kappa_B T} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Micro-canonical ensemble describes itself by Lagrange multipliers α, β [2]:

$$\begin{aligned}
W &= \prod_i w(n_i, g_i) = \prod_i \frac{g_i!}{n_i! (g_i - n_i)!} \\
\Rightarrow f(n_i) &= \ln(W) + \alpha (N - \sum n_i) + \beta (E - \sum n_i \epsilon_i) \\
\Rightarrow (\text{By Stirling's approximation}) n_i &= \arg \max_{n_i} f(n_i) = \frac{g_i}{e^{\alpha + \beta \epsilon_i} + 1}
\end{aligned}$$

where W is the number of ways that total of particles can be classified into energy levels according to their energies [3] with a fixed number of particle N and a fixed energy E .

So, it would be natural to say that at least both Einstein field equation and conservation of CPT affect phase transition. If then, the model could be rearranged by maximal consideration within given concepts from Fermi-Dirac statistics.

6 Chain of Ensembles with Conservation of CPT

The two perspectives are each related with theory of relativity and CPT conservation. Then why does summation of series product in power of e corresponds to *LFO*? And why does maximized number of ways in combination of particle corresponds to conservation in *SR* and *CR*?

By terms of *LFO* and conservation in *SR* and *CR*, assuming that canonical and micro-canonical ensemble has equal conclusion:

$$\begin{aligned}
(\text{LFO Chain}) &\equiv (\text{CPT Conservation}) \\
\Rightarrow Z_i(N)/Z_i(N-1) &= e^{-\mu/k_B T} = \left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\epsilon_i/\kappa_B T}} \\
\Rightarrow \left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\epsilon_i/\kappa_B T}} - \frac{1}{e^{\mu/k_B T}} + 1 &= 1 \\
\Rightarrow \left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{(\epsilon_i - \mu)/\kappa_B T}} - 1 + e^{\mu/\kappa_B T} &= e^{\mu/\kappa_B T} \\
\Rightarrow \left(\left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\epsilon_i/\kappa_B T}} + 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{-\mu/\kappa_B T}} - 1 &= e^{\mu/\kappa_B T} \\
\Rightarrow \left(\left(\frac{1}{\bar{n}_i} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\epsilon_i/\kappa_B T}} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{e^{-\mu/\kappa_B T}} - 1 &= -e^{\mu/\kappa_B T}
\end{aligned}$$

While in CPT conservation table [6]:

		Optimal t	With PE	With ME	With OE
Original	(Expectation)	E	Not specific	Not specific	Not specific
Type 1	SR = CR	In symmetry	With T asymmetry	Not specific	Not specific
Type 2	SR - CR > 0	With P, T asymmetry	With P, T asymmetry	With P, T asymmetry	Not specific
Type 3	CR - SR > 0	With C, P, T asymmetry	With C, P, T asymmetry	With C, P, T asymmetry	With C, P, T asymmetry

Table 1: Asymmetry-error relations

Within equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
TEO &= E = E_{Type1} + E_{Type2} + E_{Type3} \\
\Rightarrow E_{Type1} &= LFO \cdot TEO \cdot (1 - PE(E)), \\
E_{Type2} &= LFO \cdot TEO \cdot (1 - PE(E))(1 - ME(E)) + \sum SR - \sum CR, \\
E_{Type3} &= LFO \cdot TEO \cdot (1 - PE(E))(1 - ME(E))(1 - OE(E)) + \sum SR - \sum CR \\
\Rightarrow E &= LFO \cdot TEO \cdot ((1 - PE(E)) + (1 - PE(E))(1 - ME(E)) + (1 - PE(E))(1 - ME(E))(1 - OE(E)))
\end{aligned}$$

Assuming that $\alpha = 1 - PE(E)$, $\beta = 1 - ME(E)$, and $\gamma = 1 - OE(E)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
LFO \cdot (\alpha + \alpha\beta + \alpha\beta\gamma) &= 1 \\
\alpha + \beta &= 1 - \gamma
\end{aligned}$$

And by definition of PE:

$$\begin{aligned}
1 - \gamma &= LFO \\
\Rightarrow (\alpha + \beta)\alpha(1 + \beta + \beta\gamma) &= 1 \\
\Rightarrow 1 + \beta + \beta\gamma &= \frac{1}{(\alpha + \beta)\alpha} \\
\Rightarrow 1 &= \frac{1}{(\alpha + \beta)\alpha\beta} - \frac{1}{\beta} - \gamma \\
\Rightarrow \gamma &= \frac{1}{\beta} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha(\alpha + \beta)} - 1 \right) - 1
\end{aligned}$$

7 Chain of Ensembles in Phase Transition

So to here, it has been discussed that three modes of statistical ensemble takes place in CPT conservation. Then what could be more to be extended in form of these canonicals? Let take a look at gas state equation – and assume in any premise that given on its kinetic energy forms T(temperature).

$$nRT = PV$$

where nR is mass by definition, T is kinetic energy of particles, P forms outward(or inward) force(or tensor if its more understandable) energy, and V as volume that mass takes.

With this view, it is clear that there are timely difference somewhere between equation mark. Whether it is before the equation sign or after, every particle makes its composition by the given value before. So it would be plausible to assume that there could be at least several considerations in result of interaction in particles.

7.1 Partial to Whole: nR for Matter

7.2 Kinetic Energy: T for Temperature

7.3 Pressure: P for Convergence and Divergence

7.4 Volume: V for Given Space

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